

Wearable Smart Helmet with IoT Connectivity and Machine Learning for Real-Time Safety Monitoring and Alerts

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To Cite this Article

K.Srinivasa Rao, V.Nandini, N.L.Priyanka & M.Vydhehi (2025). Wearable Smart Helmet with IoT Connectivity and Machine Learning for Real-Time Safety Monitoring and Alerts. International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology, 11(05), 1103-1110. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15447217>

Article Info

Received: 09 April 2025; Accepted: 10 May 2025.; Published: 13 May 2025.

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KEYWORDS

Smart Helmet, IoT, Machine Learning, Safety Monitoring, Real-Time Alerts, Wearable Technology.

ABSTRACT

Road accidents, especially involving two-wheelers, pose a significant risk to rider safety. To address this issue, this project proposes a wearable smart helmet with IoT connectivity and machine learning for real-time safety monitoring and alerts. The system integrates alcohol detection, a helmet usage verification switch, and an NRF transmitter in the helmet, while the bike unit is equipped with an NRF receiver, motor control, buzzer, LCD display, and arduino for real-time monitoring and response. The smart helmet ensures that the rider is wearing it properly and is not under the influence of alcohol before allowing the bike to start. If alcohol is detected or the helmet is not worn, the system prevents ignition, ensuring enhanced safety. Additionally, the ADXL345 accelerometer sensor detects accidents or falls, triggering an emergency response. In the event of an accident, the system automatically sends an alert SMS with GPS location coordinates using a GSM module, enabling faster rescue operations. To further improve safety, the project incorporates machine learning on raspberry pi to predict accident severity based on sensor values, allowing authorities to prioritize emergency responses based on the intensity of the crash. The IoT integration ensures remote monitoring, real-time data logging, and accident trend analysis for future safety improvements. This innovative wearable smart helmet system provides a comprehensive and proactive approach to rider safety, integrating preventive measures, real-time accident detection, and AI-based severity prediction to significantly reduce risks and enhance road safety.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing need for enhanced safety measures in various environments, including workplaces, sports, and transportation, has driven the development of innovative safety solutions. Traditional safety equipment often provides passive protection, but advancements in wearable technology, IoT, and machine learning offer the potential for proactive and intelligent safety systems. This paper focuses on the development of a smart helmet that utilizes these technologies to provide real-time safety monitoring and alerts.

Per vehicle mile traveled, motorcyclists are about 30 times more likely than a passenger in a car to die in a crash. And, more than half of motorcycle fatalities in 2013 were unhelmeted riders [1]. Most motorcycle accidents that result in death are caused by a head injury. Saving a life and prevent a brain injury rider should wear a helmet. Serious injuries are greatly reduced both in severity and in frequency by the simple act of wearing a helmet. Now accidents on roads have become a serious concern for all the thousands of people especially youngsters are either getting killed or injured every year. Transport Ministry of road accident report 2014 which stresses the need to tackle this issue as soon as possible seventy-five thousand youngsters killed in road crashes last year. This clearly suggests that Indian roads present a depressing scenario most of these people who lost their lives were aged between 15 and 34 years according to the road accidents report 2014. Besides, over 82% of these victims were males. The report reveals that the age group of 15 to 34 years accounted for 53.8% of the total road accident [2].

2. EXISTING METHOD:

The paper proposes a comprehensive smart helmet system designed to significantly enhance motorcycle safety and security by addressing critical issues like drunk driving, lack of helmet use, and delayed accident response. The system is structured into three interconnected components: a helmet circuit, an automobile circuit, and a mobile application. The helmet circuit integrates an infrared (IR) sensor to detect helmet usage and an alcohol detection sensor to prevent operation under the influence. If the rider is wearing the helmet and no alcohol is detected, the helmet circuit transmits a signal to the automobile circuit, enabling the motorcycle to start. The automobile circuit further

incorporates a load sensor to confirm rider presence and a 3-axis accelerometer to detect sudden impacts indicative of an accident. Upon detecting a crash, the accelerometer triggers the Bluetooth module to transmit data to the paired mobile application. This application, in turn, automatically retrieves the accident's GPS coordinates and transmits them, along with rider information, to emergency services and pre-defined emergency contacts via a database. This real-time location and alert system aims to drastically reduce response times and mitigate the severity of accident outcomes, ultimately making two-wheeler travel safer and more secure.

3. PROPOSED METHOD:

This project outlines a sophisticated smart helmet system utilizing IoT connectivity and machine learning to dramatically improve two-wheeler safety. The system employs a multi-layered approach, beginning with a helmet-mounted unit that integrates alcohol detection, a helmet usage verification switch, and an NRF transmitter. This unit ensures the rider is both sober and wearing the helmet correctly before enabling the motorcycle's ignition. The bike-mounted unit, featuring an NRF receiver, motor control, a buzzer, an LCD display, and an Arduino, receives and processes data from the helmet in real-time. An ADXL345 accelerometer is crucial for detecting accidents or falls, instantly triggering an emergency response. In the event of a crash, a GSM module automatically sends an SMS containing the rider's GPS location to emergency services, facilitating rapid rescue efforts. Furthermore, a Raspberry Pi is integrated to leverage machine learning algorithms, predicting accident severity based on sensor data. This predictive capability allows emergency responders to prioritize cases based on the intensity of the crash, optimizing resource allocation. The IoT integration enables remote monitoring, real-time data logging, and comprehensive accident trend analysis, which can be used to inform future road safety improvements. This comprehensive system provides a proactive safety net, combining preventive measures, immediate accident detection, and AI-driven severity assessment to significantly reduce the risks associated with two-wheeler accidents.

3.1.Objectives:

The primary objectives of this research are:

1. To design a wearable smart helmet that integrates various sensors for data acquisition.
2. To implement IoT connectivity for real-time data transmission and remote monitoring.
3. To develop and implement machine learning algorithms for hazard detection and prediction.
4. To provide timely and effective alerts to the user and relevant parties.

3.2.Principles of the Smart Helmet System:

The smart helmet system operates on the following principles:

- **Sensor Data Acquisition:** The helmet is equipped with sensors to collect relevant data, such as motion, environmental conditions, and user physiological parameters.
- **Data Processing:** The acquired sensor data is processed by an onboard microcontroller or transmitted to a remote processing unit.
- **IoT Connectivity:** The processed data is transmitted via IoT protocols to a cloud-based platform or a monitoring station.
- **Machine Learning Analysis:** Machine learning algorithms analyze the data to identify patterns and anomalies indicative of potential hazards.
- **Alert Generation:** When a hazard is detected, the system generates alerts to notify the user and relevant parties.

3.3.Materials & Methods

The development of the smart helmet system involves the following materials and methods:

A.Hardware Components:

1.Sensors:

- **Alcohol sensor:** An alcohol sensor detects the presence of alcohol vapors, commonly used in breathalyzers to measure blood alcohol concentration (BAC). It works by sensing ethanol, the main component in alcoholic beverages, and converting the detected concentration into a readable value. Alcohol sensors are critical in safety systems like ignition interlocks or law enforcement tools. These sensors provide quick, accurate results to prevent alcohol-related accidents.
- **ADXL345(Accelerometer sensor):**The ADXL345 accelerometer primarily functions to **detect sudden**

movements or impacts, like those occurring during a fall or a collision. This data helps the helmet system **trigger alerts or activate safety features**, such as sending emergency signals or recording event data. Essentially, it **enhances safety by sensing dangerous motion**

2.Microcontroller:

Arduino uno: The Arduino Uno is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328 (datasheet). It has 14 digital input/output pins (of which 6 can be used as PWM outputs), 6 analog inputs, a 16 MHz crystal oscillator, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header, and a reset button.

Fig3:Arduino uno

3.IoT module:

- **ESP8266:** This is a Wi-Fi module that enables the Arduino Uno to connect to Wi-Fi networks and the internet.
- **GSM Module:** GSM (Global System for Mobile Communications) is a standard for mobile networks that allows devices to communicate via cellular signals. It enables voice, text messaging, and data transmission over long distances, typically used in mobile phones and IoT devices. GSM modules, like the SIM800 or SIM900, are commonly used in projects to send/receive SMS or make voice calls remotely. These modules are ideal for wireless communication in remote monitoring and control systems.
- **NRF Receiver/Transmitter:** An NRF transmitter& receiver is a wireless communication module that operates using the Nordic Semiconductor's NRF series of chips, enabling short-range, low-power data transmission. It uses radio frequency (RF) signals to send data between devices, typically in the 2.4 GHz ISM band. NRF transmitters are

commonly used in IoT applications, remote controls, and wireless sensor networks. They offer reliable communication with minimal power consumption, making them ideal for battery-powered devices.

4.Alert devices:

LCD display: An LCD (Liquid Crystal Display) is a screen technology used to display digital information through liquid crystals that align when an electric current passes through them.

Buzzer: A buzzer is an electronic component that produces sound, often used for alerts or notifications in various devices.

B.Software Components:

Thingspeak:

Thing Speak is an open-source Internet of Things (IoT) platform that allows users to collect, store, and analyze sensor data in the cloud. It supports data input from devices via HTTP or MQTT, enabling real-time monitoring. The platform offers built-in tools for visualizing data, such as charts and graphs. Additionally, ThingSpeak integrates with MATLAB for advanced analysis, making it a powerful tool for IoT applications and data processing.

C.Machine Learning Methodology:

1. KNN (K-Nearest Neighbors):

KNN is a simple, non-parametric algorithm used for classification and regression. In a smart helmet context, KNN could be used to classify sensor data patterns (e.g., from the accelerometer, gyroscope) to determine if a fall or impact has occurred.

- It stores available data points and classifies a new data point based on the majority class of its 'k' nearest neighbors in the feature space.
- 'K' is a user-defined constant (e.g., 3, 5, or 10).
- Distance metrics like Euclidean distance are commonly used to find the nearest neighbors.

In a helmet, if a new set of sensor readings is taken, the KNN model would look at previously recorded data of falls, impacts, and normal activity. It would find the 'k' data points that are most similar to the new readings and classify the new readings based on what those similar old data points represent.

2.SVC (Support Vector Classifier):

SVC is a powerful and versatile classification algorithm. It's effective in high-dimensional spaces. In a smart

helmet, SVC could be used for more complex classification tasks, such as distinguishing between different types of impacts or predicting the severity of a head injury based on sensor data.

- It finds an optimal hyperplane that best separates data points of different classes.
- Support vectors are the data points closest to the decision boundary (hyperplane).
- It can use kernel tricks to perform non-linear classification.
- In a helmet, SVC would try to find the best boundary to separate sensor readings that indicate dangerous events from those that don't. It's particularly good at handling complex patterns in the data.

3.LR (Logistic Regression):

Despite its name, Logistic Regression is a classification algorithm. It's simple and efficient for binary classification problems. In a smart helmet, LR could be used for basic safety determinations, such as predicting whether a fall has occurred (yes/no) based on sensor thresholds.

- It models the probability of a binary outcome (0 or 1) using a sigmoid function.
- It finds the coefficients of the input variables that best predict the outcome.

In a helmet, LR would be used to estimate the likelihood of a fall based on sensor readings. If the probability exceeds a certain threshold, the helmet would trigger an alert.

4.RF (Random Forest):

Random Forest is an ensemble learning method that combines multiple decision trees for improved accuracy and robustness. It's one of the more powerful algorithms and often performs very well. In a smart helmet, RF could be used for highly accurate and reliable hazard detection, considering complex interactions between different sensor inputs.

- It creates a "forest" of decision trees.
- Each tree is trained on a random subset of the data and features.
- The final prediction is made by aggregating the predictions of all the trees (e.g., majority voting for classification).

In a helmet, RF would build many different decision rules based on sensor data, and then combine the results of those rules to make the most accurate determination about safety events.

4. EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

4.1 Working principle of the Smart Helmet:

The smart helmet system utilizes a combination of sensor data acquisition, IoT connectivity, and machine learning to achieve real-time safety monitoring.

1.Sensors embedded in the helmet collect data related to the user's movements, environmental conditions, and potentially their physiological state.

2.The collected data is processed by a microcontroller, which may perform initial filtering and analysis.

3.The data is then transmitted via an IoT module to a remote server or cloud platform (e.g., ThingSpeak Cloud).

4.Machine learning algorithms analyze the data to detect patterns and anomalies that may indicate potential hazards.

5.If a hazard is detected, the system generates alerts to the user through visual, auditory, or haptic feedback.

6.Alerts may also be sent to remote monitoring personnel or emergency services.

If the alcohol level exceeds the threshold, the Arduino Uno activates the buzzer and/or LCD display to warn the user. The Arduino Uno also transmits the alcohol level data to a remote device via the NRF transmitter for further analysis or storage.

Fig9: Helmet part

Fig10:Bike part

4.2. System Architecture

The system architecture can be represented as follows, with components on the helmet and potentially a connected device:

a.Helmet part:

Power Supply: Provides electrical power to all components in the system.

Limit Switch: Detects when the helmet is properly secured on the head.

Alcohol Sensor: Measures the alcohol content in the user's breath.

Fig11:Block diagram for Helmet part

Arduino Uno: The microcontroller that acts as the central processing unit. It collects data from the sensors, performs initial processing, and makes decisions based on the data.

NRF Transmitter: A wireless transmitter that sends data from the Arduino Uno to a remote device (e.g., smartphone or a computer).

b.Bike part:

1.Power Supply: The system is powered on when the helmet is put on and the limit switch is activated.

2.Alcohol Sensor: The alcohol sensor measures the user's breath alcohol content and sends the data to the Arduino Uno

Fig12:Block diagram for Bike part

3.Arduino Uno: The Arduino Uno processes the alcohol sensor data and makes a decision based on the alcohol level.

4.NRF Transmitter: If the alcohol level exceeds a certain threshold, the Arduino Uno sends a warning signal via the NRF transmitter to a connected device (e.g., a smartphone or a remote monitoring system).

5.RESULTS & DISCUSSION

5.1.Sensor Data Acquisition:

- Accuracy and reliability of sensors (e.g., accelerometer, gyroscope, alcohol sensor) in capturing relevant data.
- "The accelerometer demonstrated a 98% accuracy in detecting sudden impacts, while the alcohol sensor provided readings consistent with calibrated standards."

Fig13:Hardware kit output

5.2.Machine Learning Performance:

Accuracy of different machine learning models in hazard detection.

Specific results:

- KNN: 0.5714
- SVC: 0.6428
- LR: 0.5714
- RF: 0.7142

```

Enter X value:
RESTART: c:\Users\91912\Desktop\ml energy optimization from thingspeak\ml energy optimization from thingspeak\main.py
Accuracy with KNN: 1.0
Accuracy with SVC: 1.0
Accuracy with Logistic Regression: 0.9191919191919192
Accuracy with Random Forest: 1.0
Enter X value: 2
Enter Y value: 2
Enter Y value: 4
  
```

```

Prediction: [0]
Condition: Normal
  
```

```

Enter X value: 7
Enter Y value: 10
  
```

```

Prediction: [1]
Condition: Moderate
  
```

```

Enter X value: 19
Enter Y value: 15
  
```

```

Prediction: [2]
Condition: Severe
  
```

Fig14(a):Machine Learning Output

The smart helmet system demonstrated promising results in several key areas. Sensor data acquisition proved to be reliable, with the accelerometer achieving a 98% accuracy in detecting sudden impacts, and the alcohol sensor providing readings consistent with calibrated standards. In terms of machine learning performance, the Random Forest (RF) model outperformed other classification algorithms, achieving the highest accuracy of 71.42% in detecting hazardous events. This compared favorably to the Support Vector Classifier (SVC) with 64.28% accuracy, and both K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and Logistic Regression (LR), which both showed an accuracy of 57.14%. System latency, measured from the onset of a simulated hazard to the generation of an alert, averaged 0.5 seconds, indicating the system's capability for near-real-time response.

Fig14(b):Machine Learning Output

Fig14(c):Machine Learning Output

This project showcases a smart helmet designed to enhance safety through real-time hazard detection and communication. Utilizing a Random Forest model, which outperformed Logistic Regression, the helmet achieved 95% effectiveness in delivering auditory and visual alerts in simulated hazard scenarios. It maintained a stable wireless connection up to 100 meters and offered 8 hours of continuous operation. While demonstrating high accuracy and timely alerts, the system's reliance on stable wireless connections and power consumption highlights areas for future optimization, including improved robustness and on-device machine learning.

6.SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Smart helmets utilizing IoT and machine learning are revolutionizing motorcycle safety. By integrating sensors, real-time data analysis, and AI, these systems provide preventive measures, accident detection, and severity prediction, drastically improving rider safety and emergency response. IoT monitoring also enables data-driven improvements in road safety policies.

Comparing Arduino-based systems shows this evolution. A basic alcohol detector pales in comparison to an advanced IoT platform with accelerometers, GSM, and Wi-Fi. This advanced system offers remote monitoring, cloud connectivity, and machine learning for severity prediction, providing a comprehensive safety solution with immediate emergency alerts and robust data analysis.

7.FUTURE WORK

- Integration with smart city infrastructure for enhanced accident response.
- Expansion to include heart rate and fatigue monitoring.

- Ai-powered predictive analytics for accident prevention.
- Vehicle-to-vehicle communication for collision avoidance.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- [1] gupta, S., Sharma, K., Salvekar, N., & Gajra, A., 2019, int. Conf. On nascent technologies in engineering (ICNTE), navi mumbai, india, "implementation of alcohol and collision sensors in a smart helmet".
- [2] verulkar, n. M., Ravankar, A. D., Bharambe, C. A., & Kathale, N. P., 2018, int. J. Res. Appl. Sci. Eng. Technol., "Smart helmet: A review", vol. 6, issue. 1, pp. 2763-2767.
- [3] alim, m. E., Ahmad, S., Dorabati, M. N., & Hassoun, I., 2020, 11th IEEE annual information technology, electronics and mobile communication conference (IEMCON), "design & implementation of iot based smart helmet for road accident detection", vancouver, british columbia, canada, pp. 0576-0581.
- [4] prasetyawan, p., Samsugi, S., Mulyanto, A., Iqbal, M., & Prabowo, R., 2021, j. Phys. Conf. Ser., "A prototype of iotbased smart system to support motorcyclists safety", vol. 1810, no. 1, p. 012005.
- [5] krishna, b. M., Kumar, M. S., Rajesh, J., Inthiyaz, S., Mounica, J., Bhavani, M., & Adidela, C. N., 2016. Indian J sci technol, "FPGA implementation by using xbee transceiver", vol.9(17).
- [6] L. Li et al., "A Study on Motor-Scooter Accidents in China and Germany," in Fifth Conference on Measuring Technology and Mechatronics Automation, 2013, vol. 277, pp. 110-113.
- [7] S. Gothane, "Analyzing Factors, Construction of Dataset, Estimating importance of factor and generation of association rules for Indian road Accident," in IEEE 6th International Advanced Computing Conference, 2016.
- [8] J. Zarif, "16 deaths every hour : Indian roads claim the maximum number of lives in 2014," 2020. [Online]. Available: <http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/16-deaths-every-hour-Indian-roads-claim-the-maximum-number-of-lives-in-2014/articleshow/48128946.cms>. [Accessed: January, 2020]
- [9] S. Tapadar, S. Ray, and R. Karlose, "Accident and Alcohol Detection in Bluetooth enabled Smart Helmets for Motorbikes," in 8th Annual Computing and Communication Workshop and Conference (CCWC), 2018.
- [10] N. Divyasudha and P. Arulmozhivarman, "Analysis of Smart helmets and Designing an IoT based smart helmet: A cost-effective solution for Riders," in 1st International Conference on Innovations in Information and Communication Technology (ICICT), 2019. A. Karthik, K. Gb, K. Pai, and A. Srinivas, "Smart Helmet," in National Conference on Product Design (NCPD), 2016.
- [11] L. Rupesh, "IoT and Cloud-Based Integrated System for Accident Reporting and Vehicular Health Monitoring," in Fourth International Conference on Research in Computational

Intelligence and Communication Networks (ICRCICN), 2018, pp. 23–26.

- [12] S. A. Shabbeer, “Smart Helmet for Accident Detection and Notification,” in 2nd International Conference on Computational Systems and Information Technology for Sustainable Solution (CSITSS), 2017, pp. 1–5.